

The antidepressant, sertraline, impacts growth and reproduction in the benthic deposit feeder, *Tubifex tubifex*

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ABSTRACT

Among emerging contaminants, pharmaceuticals are considered one of the most pertinent substances that may threaten aquatic ecosystems. Pharmaceuticals are designed to be directed at specific metabolic- and molecular pathways. Thus, they are assumed to be still biologically active when entering the ecosystem and may result in unpremeditated impacts on non-target organisms. One of the most widely used selective serotonin reuptake inhibitors, sertraline (an antidepressant), is regularly found in aquatic environments. However, knowledge about the effects, and in particular, of sediment-associated sertraline in benthic invertebrates is limited. We examined the impacts of chronic exposure (28 d) to sediment-associated sertraline (3.3, 33, 330 µg/g dw sed.) on survival, growth and reproduction in the deposit-feeding oligochaete, *Tubifex tubifex*. Sertraline significantly decreased *T. tubifex* survival and growth. Worms exposed to high sertraline concentrations (330 µg/g) had a lower growth rate and reproduction, as indicated by a significantly lower number of cumulated cocoons. Worms exposed to an environmentally relevant concentration (3.3 µg/g) decreased growth but maintained a reproduction rate similar to that of the control. The implications are that adult worms exposed to high sertraline concentrations presumably required more energy for maintenance and detoxification, thereby reducing available energy for reproduction and growth. This represents a trade-off between survival, reproduction and growth. In contrast, *T. tubifex* exposed to environmentally relevant concentrations allocated more energy to reproduction by slightly increasing the number of cocoons produced and reducing growth. However, the quantity and quality of offspring may be impacted as we observed fewer juveniles in the environmentally relevant treatment than in the control. Overall, the results indicate that sediment-associated sertraline is bioavailable and negatively impacts *T. tubifex* survival, growth, and reproduction even at environmentally relevant concentrations.

1. Introduction

Pharmaceuticals are recognised as one of the most pertinent substances among the emerging contaminants that potentially result in threats to aquatic ecosystems (Jones et al., 2003; Bottoni et al., 2010; Corcoran et al., 2010; Guzel et al., 2019). There is an increasing awareness regarding the presence of pharmaceuticals in the aquatic environment due to a universal increase in usage and their chemo-physical characteristics, and since these compounds may not be efficiently removed in the wastewater treatment system (Conn et al., 2006). As pharmaceuticals are designed to be directed at specific metabolic- and molecular pathways in organisms, they are assumed to be still biologically active when entering the ecosystem, which can lead to unpremeditated impacts on non-target organisms (Huerta et al., 2012). Among the various types of pharmaceuticals, antidepressants are

considered one of the biggest concerns as they are widely prescribed globally due to growing trends in mental health problems and psychiatric disorders (Calisto and Esteves, 2009). Selective serotonin reuptake inhibitors (SSRIs) are commonly used as a treatment for depression and anxiety and act by increasing the level of serotonin that is responsible for the neuromodulation of numerous hormone-dependent physiological processes in the body (Rodríguez and Renaud, 1980). However, SSRIs in the environment may cause undesirable impacts on non-target organisms, affecting reproduction in invertebrates (Rodríguez and Renaud, 1980; Valenti et al., 2009; Christen et al., 2010). According to Nation (2008), serotonin stimulates the production of ecdysteroids, ecdysone, and juvenile hormones in invertebrates, which control oogenesis and vitellogenesis. As serotonin is an important neuromodulator of sexual function in invertebrates, SSRIs may affect spawning and oocyte maturation, as shown for some bivalves and crustaceans where several

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reproductive events are regulated by the neurotransmitter serotonin (Fong et al., 2003; Nation, 2008). Furthermore, it is known that SSRIs increase the size of ovaries and oocytes in crayfish and induce reproductive processes in bivalves (Kulkarni et al., 1992; Fong, 1998; Fong et al., 2003).

Most ecotoxicological studies on SSRIs have focused on water exposure, and only a few have examined the impact of sediment-associated SSRIs on benthic invertebrates. Sediments may act as a sink for pharmaceuticals, thus placing benthic organisms at risk of pharmaceutical exposure (Schultz et al., 2010; Xu et al., 2014). Thus, pharmaceuticals may enter the aquatic food web following sediment ingestion and subsequent bioaccumulation in deposit-feeding invertebrates (Grabicova et al., 2015). Benthic invertebrates are vital components of the aquatic food web, constituting a major part of fish diets. Thus, it is important to understand the uptake and effects of sediment-associated pharmaceuticals in benthic organisms.

Sertraline (log Kow = 5.3), a common SSRI, is found in surface water and wastewater effluents at levels up to 5.1 µg/L (Kleywegt et al., 2019; Metcalfe et al., 2010; Schultz and Furlong, 2008), and even reaching 17 µg/L in untreated sewage (Styrishave et al., 2011). However, the lack of measured sertraline sediment concentrations challenges our ability to assess the range of environmental sertraline concentrations (Black and Armbrust, 2015; Konieczny et al., 2018; NEA, 2019; Junior et al., 2022a, 2022b). Since sertraline is a hydrophobic compound, it is estimated that the environmental sediment concentrations of sertraline are considerably higher than in the overlying water. Indeed, antidepressants, such as sertraline, have higher affinity for sediment than sludge (Junior et al., 2022a, 2022b). Levels of sertraline in sediments have been measured to be 1.98 µg/g (Junior et al., 2020). Sertraline has been detected in aquatic organisms (Brooks et al., 2005; Ramirez et al., 2009; Schultz et al., 2010); for example, concentrations range from 0.1 to 10 mg/kg in fish tissues from polluted streams (Brooks et al., 2005). At the same time, Rodrigues et al. (2015) examined sertraline accumulations and effects in the crab, *C. maenas*, from a moderately contaminated and a low-impacted estuary by exposing them to environmentally relevant and high levels of sertraline (0.05, 5, 500 µg/L). They found that *C. maenas* exhibited decreased acetylcholinesterase activity, indicative of ventilatory and locomotory dysfunction, inhibition of antioxidant enzymes and increased oxidative damage at ≥ 0.05 g/L of sertraline. Xie et al. (2015) investigated the effect on the crucian carp exposed to sertraline (4.36, 21.3 and 116 µg/L) for 7 days and discovered significant increases in various enzymic activities and swimming activity with a decrease in shoaling tendency, feeding rate and food consumption under sertraline exposure.

Tubificid oligochaetes constitute one of the most common benthic taxa and are considered useful as a bioassay test organism, especially when assessing reproduction due to their short reproduction cycle and recognisable life history stages: cocoons, newly hatched worms, immature worms, mature worms, and breeding individuals (Reynoldson et al., 1991). *Tubifex tubifex* is a benthic cosmopolitan oligochaete inhabiting freshwater sediments (Milbrink, 1983; Crottini et al., 2008). *T. tubifex* thrives in contaminated (e.g., PAHs, metals, and pharmaceuticals) sites and is considered at particular risk of contaminant exposure from sediment via ingestion and via water while irrigating. *T. tubifex* is a significant food source for other organisms in the freshwater ecosystem (Milbrink, 1983; Crottini et al., 2008). *T. tubifex* was also selected as a model organism due to its tolerance to a wide range of ecological parameters and its ease of cultivation in the laboratory.

This study was motivated by the deficiency of peer-reviewed knowledge about the effects of sertraline in sediment systems. We examined the long-term toxicity of the antidepressant, sertraline, by exposing *T. tubifex* to a range of sediment-associated sertraline concentrations using mortality, growth and reproduction as endpoints.

2. Materials and methods

2.1. Test chemicals

Sertraline hydrochloride (purity > 98 %) was acquired from Sigma-Aldrich (Flanders, New Jersey, USA). Sertraline stock solutions were prepared in methanol and stored at -20 °C.

2.2. Sediment preparation and spiking

Sediment was collected at Munkholmbroen in Isefjord, Roskilde, Denmark (55° 40'25"N 11° 48'44"E), in October 2021 by scraping off the top few centimetres of the sediment surface. The sediment was handled as described by Ramskov et al. (2015), Thit et al. (2021) and Grønlund et al. (2023). Briefly, sediment was wet sieved in the laboratory to ≤ 250 µm using Tubifex medium and frozen until use either for Tubifex rearing or experimental purposes. Before spiking, the sediment (≤ 63 µm) was defrosted, washed with *T. tubifex* medium, and homogenised using an immersion blender. The experimental sediment had a moisture content of 74 % and an organic content of 13.3 %. The sediment was spiked by adding 50 µL of the sertraline stock solution to a known amount of wet sediment. A total of 4 sertraline concentrations were prepared: 0, 3.3, 33 and 330 µg/g sediment dry weight (dw). The same volume of the solvent (methanol) was added for the control. The sediment was then placed on a shaking table at 350 rpm for 24 h to evaporate the solvent and homogenise the sediment. Subsequently, the sediment was mixed thoroughly using a metal spoon, and wet sediments were transferred to each experimental scintillation vial.

2.3. Chemical analysis

The extraction procedure used in this study was adapted from Santos et al. (2016) who analysed psychiatric drugs in sediment. Spiked sediment samples were frozen at -20 °C and lyophilised. The sediments were then ground in a grinder and passed through a 0.25 mm sieve to obtain a homogeneous sample for extraction and analysis. 0.5 g of the sieved sediment was weighed into a 50 mL polypropylene extract tube, and 10 mL of ultra-pure water was added to each tube. The tube was vortexed for 30 s to thoroughly mix the sample and water. Subsequently, 15 mL of 2 % ammonium hydroxide in acetonitrile was added to the tubes. The tube was vortexed for another 30 s to ensure proper sample mixing with the ammonium hydroxide solution. QuEChERS original salts were added to the mixture, and the mixture was immediately manually shaken to facilitate the extraction process. After shaking, the tube was vortexed for 1 min to ensure complete extraction of the target compounds. The sample was then centrifuged at 4000 rpm for 5 min to separate the liquid phases. After centrifugation, 12 mL of the acetonitrile layer containing the extracted compounds was transferred into a 15 mL dispersive SPE tube. The dispersive SPE tube contained 150 mg of primary secondary amine (PSA) and 900 mg of magnesium sulfate (MgSO₄). The tube was vortexed for 1 min to ensure proper mixing of the extract with the dispersive SPE materials. After vortexing, the tube was centrifuged at 4000 rpm for 5 min to separate the solid and liquid phases. Following centrifugation, 9 mL of the extract was transferred to a glass tube. The extract was evaporated to dryness under a gentle stream of nitrogen to remove the solvent. Once dry, the extract was reconstituted with 500 µL of methanol. Samples were analysed using gas chromatography-mass spectrometry (GC-MS), Agilent 6890N Network Gas Chromatograph with 5973N Mass Selective Detector, and coupled with the DB5-MS column.

2.4. Rearing conditions for *T. tubifex*

T. tubifex were purchased from Bonnies Dyrecenter (DK), where the worms were stored at 4 °C. *T. tubifex* were acclimatised in the laboratory in glass aquaria with uncontaminated natural sediments collected by

Munkholmbroen. *T. tubifex* medium (artificial freshwater) was prepared following OECD guideline 315 (OECD, 2008). In short, a 2 L stock solution was made by dissolving calcium chloride (11.76 g/L CaCl₂·2H₂O, 10035-04-8, Merck), magnesium sulphate (4.93 g/L MgSO₄·7H₂O, 10034-99-8, Merck), sodium bicarbonate (2.59 g/L, NaH₂CO₃, 144-55-8, Merck), and potassium chloride (0.23 g/L KCl, 7447-40-7, Merck) in deionised water. Then, the total volume was made up to 25 L with deionised water, aerated until oxygen saturation was achieved, and stored at 20 °C. Aeration was provided using a pump, a silicon tube, and an aeration stone.

2.5. Experimental setup

Sexually mature *T. tubifex* (indicated by the presence of testes or ovaries) with similar size ranges (1.5–2 cm) were selected from the same laboratory culture using a plastic sieve (500 µm) to ensure all individuals belonged to the same age class. Worms were observed and measured using millimetric paper under the microscope to avoid significant size differences among treatments. Randomised groupings were generated using Microsoft Excel, and one-way ANOVA was performed to ensure no significant differences among groups. The worms were placed individually in 96-multiwell plates with aerated *T. tubifex* medium. A picture of each worm was taken, and the initial length was measured using ImageJ. There were 5 replicates, each with 4 individual worms, per concentration. The experimental vials (20 mL scintillation vials) contained 5 g of wet spiked or control sediment and 15 mL of aerated *T. tubifex* medium. The vials were maintained in the dark at 20 ± 2 °C during the 28-day experimental duration. Every 7 days until experimental end, worms were removed from the vials using a 250 µm metal sieve (Reynoldson et al., 1991), and the number of original adult worms, number of juveniles, number of cocoons with eggs and empty cocoons were counted. Subsequently, the original adult worms and the cocoons with eggs were transferred to freshly prepared scintillation vials with newly spiked sediments (same concentrations). The sertraline sediment concentration was measured at experimental start and after 7 days (i.e., the longest the sediment duration before the sediment was renewed). At experimental end (i.e., day 28), worms were individually placed in 96-multiwell plates with aerated *T. tubifex* medium to defecate, and the final length was recorded from pictures of each worm.

2.6. Statistical analysis

Impacts of sertraline concentrations and exposure time on growth, survival and number of cocoons with eggs collected at each time point were tested using two-way ANOVA. Data met ANOVA assumptions of normality and variance homoscedasticity. Mortality data was ArcSin transformed before statistical analyses (ANOVA test). Tukey's post-hoc tests were performed in cases with significant ANOVA to compare effects among treatments. The Pearson correlation coefficient was used to examine correlations between various endpoints. All differences were considered significant at $p < 0.05$. Correlation tests (i.e., a statistical analysis method) were used to examine the relationship between two or more variables. This method measures the strength and direction of the linear association between variables, indicating how changes in one variable correspond to changes in another. The correlation coefficient ranges from -1 to +1, representing the strength and direction of the relationship. Further, a simple linear regression analysis was performed to understand the relationship between reproduction and growth. Statistical analyses were performed using IBM SPSS 19.0 and GraphPad Prism version 10.0 software. Data are presented as mean (+/- 1 SD).

3. Results

Actual sertraline concentrations at experimental start were 2.8, 29.4 and 250 µg/g dw sediment. After 7 days of exposure, sediment concentrations were reduced by approximately 25, 65 and 70 % to 2.1 ±

0.1, 10.0 ± 1.0 and 74.7 ± 6.0 µg/g dw sediment, respectively. For clarity, results and discussions are referred to the nominal values.

3.1. Survival

Exposure time and sertraline concentrations interacted significantly ($P < 0.0001$) to affect survival (Table 1). Overall, mortality increased with increasing sertraline concentration (Fig. 1a), and no mortality was observed in control worms over the entire exposure duration. At the experimental end (day 28), mortality was significantly increased in worms in 3.3 µg/g dw sed. ($P \leq 0.0001$), 33 µg/g dw sed. ($P \leq 0.01$) and 330 µg/g dw sed. ($P \leq 0.01$). Mortality did not differ among 3.3, 33, and 330 µg/g dw sed. (all $P > 0.05$).

3.2. Growth

Overall, sediment-associated sertraline significantly ($P \leq 0.0001$) reduced the growth of *T. tubifex* with increasing concentration (Fig. 1b, Table 1). Control worms grew faster than worms exposed to 3.3 µg/g dw sed. ($P \leq 0.05$), 33 µg/g dw sed. ($P \leq 0.0001$) and 330 µg/g dw sed. ($P \leq 0.0001$), whereas there was no difference in the growth within exposed worms regardless of sertraline concentration (all $P > 0.05$).

3.3. Reproduction

Time and sertraline concentration interacted significantly ($P < 0.0001$) to affect reproduction, both assessed as the number of produced cocoons and number of juveniles (Table 1). Overall, the accumulated number of cocoons increased with exposure time for all but the highest concentration, where only one cocoon was produced from all replicates on day 14 and day 21, respectively (Fig. 2a). On day 28, worms in the control and lowest concentration (3.3 µg/g dw sed.) produced more cocoons than worms in 33 µg/g dw sed. and 330 µg/g dw sed. (Fig. 2a). The accumulated number of cocoons with eggs was significantly ($P \leq 0.0001$) higher in the control and the lowest concentration compared to in 33 and 330 µg/g dw sed (Fig. 2b). There was no difference in cocoon production between the control and 3.3 µg/g dw sed. and between 33 and 330 µg/g dw sed. (Fig. 2a–b). A delay in reproduction was observed for worms exposed to sediment-associated sertraline compared to the control worms, as cocoons were detected in the control on day 7, and the first cocoon appeared on day 14 for sertraline-exposed worms (Fig. 2a). Generally, cocoon production exhibited a high sensitivity in *T. tubifex* exposed to sertraline (Fig. 2a–b).

The number of juveniles was significantly ($P \leq 0.05$) higher in the control compared to the lowest concentration (3.3 µg/g dw sed.) on day 21 (Fig. 2c) and 33 µg/g dw sed. ($P \leq 0.00001$). Almost no juveniles were found in 330 µg/g dw sed., which made it significantly different from the control ($P \leq 0.0001$) and 3.3 µg/g dw sed. ($P \leq 0.05$) (Fig. 2c). Sertraline concentrations significantly ($P = 0.026$) decreased the number of hatched worms per empty cocoon (Table 1). The number of hatched worms per empty cocoon followed a similar trend as the

Table 1

Two-way ANOVA of effects of sertraline concentration and time on survival, growth, number of cocoons, number of juveniles and number of hatched worms per empty cocoon.

Factor	P-value				
	Survival	Growth	Cocoon number	Juvenile number	no. of hatched worms
Time × Sertraline Concentration	< 0.0001	-	< 0.0001	< 0.0001	0.094
Time Sertraline concentration	< 0.0001	-	< 0.0001	< 0.0001	0.005
Sertraline concentration	0.026	<	< 0.0001	< 0.0001	0.026
		0.0001			

Fig. 1. (a) Survival of *T. tubifex* at different sertraline concentrations over 28 days exposure (b) Worm body length related to sertraline concentration after 28 days exposure. (* = $P \leq 0.05$; ** = $P \leq 0.01$; *** = $P \leq 0.0001$).

Fig. 2. (a) Number of cocoons produced by *T. tubifex* exposed to different sediment-associated sertraline concentrations over 28 days. (b) Number of accumulated cocoons over the entire exposure period (28 days) (c) Number of juveniles under different sertraline concentrations over 28 days of exposure. (d) Number of hatched worms per observed empty cocoon under different sertraline concentrations over 28 days of exposure. (* = $P \leq 0.05$; ** = $P \leq 0.01$; *** = $P \leq 0.0001$; **** = $P \leq 0.00001$).

number of juveniles described above, but a significant decrease ($P \leq 0.01$) in the number of hatched worms in 3.3 µg/g dw sed. was only observed on day 21 (Fig. 2d). The number of hatched worms per empty cocoon was similar among the control, 3.3 and 33 µg/g dw sed. on day 28 (Fig. 2d). There was no sign of reproduction on days 21 and 28 for worms in 330 µg/g dw sed. (Fig. 2d).

3.4. Correlations test

Worm survival, growth, number of cocoons containing eggs, number

of hatched juveniles, and number of hatched juveniles per empty cocoon were significantly and negatively correlated with sertraline concentration (Table 2). In addition, growth, survival, number of cocoons and number of juveniles were significantly and positively correlated to one another: the higher the growth, the higher the number of cocoons and juveniles. No significant correlation was found between the number of hatched juveniles per empty cocoon and growth, survival and the number of juveniles.

Apart from the correlation test, a simple linear regression analysis was performed to examine how changes in growth affect the cumulated

Table 2

Correlation matrix between tested parameters. A correlation test was performed to examine the relationship between variables. The correlation coefficient ranges from -1 to $+1$, representing the strength and direction of the relationship.

	Sertraline conc.	Growth	Survival	Cocoon number	Juvenile number	Hatched juveniles
Sertraline conc.	1					
Growth	-0.507^*	1				
Survival	-0.497^*	0.530^*	1			
Cocoon number	-0.725^{**}	0.613^{**}	0.668^{**}	1		
Juvenile number	-0.681^{**}	0.735^{**}	0.709^{**}	0.760^{**}	1	
Hatched juveniles	-0.692^{**}	0.042	0.392	0.654^{**}	0.274	1

* Correlation is significant at the 0.05 level (2-tailed).

** Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).

number of cocoons (Fig. 3). A similar trend regarding the relation between growth and accumulated number of cocoons was observed for all other tested concentrations as data points were all within the 95 % confidence interval of the control, except for worms exposed to the environmentally relevant concentration, $3.3 \mu\text{g/g}$ of sertraline. The result indicates that worms exposed to low concentration of sertraline tend to reduce growth to boost reproduction.

4. Discussion

To our knowledge, this study is the first to assess the impact of sediment-associated sertraline on the reproduction of *T. tubifex* under long-term sediment exposure. Sertraline's octanol-water partition coefficient ($\log K_{ow}$) of 5.3 suggests a tendency to sorb to organic matter, which serves as a food source for deposit-feeding organisms, implying a potential for dietary sertraline uptake (Christensen et al., 2007; Minguez et al., 2014). Indeed, sertraline has been detected in several aquatic organisms, including freshwater mussels (*Dreissena polymorpha*), crayfish (*Procambarus clarkii*) and fish (*Cyprinus carpio*) (Vannini et al., 2011; Grabicova et al., 2015; Minguez et al., 2015; Rodrigues et al., 2015). There is, however, to our knowledge no information on the environmental concentrations of sertraline in sediments as most reports focus on surface water that generally appears to be in the low range (8 ng/L to $1 \mu\text{g/L}$) (Ahlford, 2012; Black and Armbrust, 2015; NEA, 2019; Guzel et al., 2019). Using the assumption of equilibrium between water and sediment, we used the equilibrium partitioning equation (Van der Kooij et al., 1991), the measured water concentration (8 ng/L to $1 \mu\text{g/L}$) and a sediment organic carbon from 0.01 to 0.12 (i.e., similar to the content of the experimental sediment), to estimate the sediment concentration of sertraline following:

$$C_{sed} = \frac{C_w \times 0.6 \times f_{oc} \times K_{ow}}{r}$$

where:

- C_{sed} = concentration in sediment (mg/kg)
- C_w = concentration in water ($\mu\text{g/L}$)
- K_{ow} of sertraline $\approx 194,083.26$
- f_{oc} = fraction of organic carbon in sediment
- r = suspended matter in sediment = 2

We estimate that the sertraline concentrations in sediment (with a f_{oc} of 0.01–0.12) range from 0.0005 to $7 \mu\text{g/g}$. Based on the sediment concentration estimate, $3.3 \mu\text{g/g}$ is considered the environmentally relevant concentration in this study, considering the common organic matter content in lakes and rivers is 1–15 % (Meyers and Teranes, 2001). The ionisation of sertraline hydrochloride (the salt form of sertraline) occurs due to an amino group ($-\text{NH}_2$) in the sertraline molecule. When sertraline hydrochloride is introduced to water, the amino group can dissociate to release a proton, forming a cation. This ionisation process is critical to consider when evaluating various fate aspects of sertraline in aqueous systems, such as solubility, distribution, and interactions (Deák et al., 2006). In this study, 80 % ($2.1 \mu\text{g/g}$) of the spiked sertraline was left in the sediments after 7 days of exposure in the lowest concentration ($3.3 \mu\text{g/g}$), but only 30 % ($74.7 \mu\text{g/g}$) was left in the highest concentration ($330 \mu\text{g/g}$). It is possible that the equilibrium adsorption capacity (q_e) of sertraline in sediments was reached, resulting in a lower amount of sertraline in the sediments compared to before exposure. Another possibility could be the flushing activity of *T. tubifex* (pers. com. Henriette Selck). Our research team observed that worm flushing seems to be an important removal pathway in the sediments system as flushing of *T. tubifex* contributed to the loss of chemicals from sediments into the overlaying water. The importance of the flushing effect in worms was also discussed by Christensen et al. (2002). More studies are needed to determine if other factors contribute to sertraline loss in sediments, such as the possibility of biotransformation of sertraline by *T. tubifex*.

In freshwater environments, which generally have a neutral pH, the ionisation of sertraline hydrochloride can lead to the formation of the cationic form of sertraline. For example, in the current study, the neutral fraction of sertraline base in water is approximately 0.27–0.86 % (i.e., $\text{pH}: 7\text{--}7.5$; $\text{pKa}: 9.56$; fraction of neutral base = $\frac{1}{1+10^{(\text{pKa}-\text{pH})}}$). Thus, at these pH levels, the majority of sertraline remains in its protonated (charged) form. In contrast, in marine environments, the pH is usually higher and more alkaline, leading to a higher ionisation of sertraline hydrochloride, resulting in a greater proportion of the cationic species (Deák et al., 2006; Kwon and Armbrust, 2008). The solubility of the cationic form may differ from the neutral form, affecting how much sertraline remains in solution and how much precipitates (Deák et al., 2006). Indeed, ionised compounds can interact strongly with negatively charged particles in sediments, which can lead to the compound being sequestered in sediments (Deák et al., 2006; Kwon and Armbrust, 2008; Burton, 2018). Besides, the different forms may impact affinity for organic matter, sediment, and biological tissues, potentially impacting bioavailability, uptake, accumulation, and elimination, and thus toxicity to aquatic organisms (Deák et al., 2006; Kwon and Armbrust, 2008). However, the hydrophobicity of sertraline indicates that it is

Fig. 3. Correlation between *T. tubifex* growth and the cumulated number of cocoons produced related to sertraline concentration following 28 days of exposure. The blue line represents the simple linear regression of the control and the corresponding 95 % confidence interval.

exceedingly sediment-associated sorption to suspended particles, such as organic debris and sediment particles, when introduced to water. This association with particles effectively reduces the concentration of sertraline in the water column, making it less available for direct interaction with aquatic organisms. Instead, sertraline becomes sequestered in the sediment, accumulating over time. Thus, benthic invertebrates will be in contact with sertraline by ingesting sediment particles or via dermal contact (Kwon and Armbrust, 2008; Junior et al., 2022a, 2022b).

Sertraline increased the mortality of *T. tubifex* in the present study. Indeed, several studies investigating the effects of SSRIs on benthic invertebrates report similar results. For example, Nentwig (2007) tested the effects of the SSRI, fluoxetine (nominal concentration: 0.64–400 µg/L), on reproduction in the freshwater mud snail, *P. antipodarum*, and reported 100 % mortality in all replicates exposed to the highest fluoxetine concentration. For acute tests, Stremmel et al. (2023) found an LC50 (96 h) of *D. magna* at 365 µg/L of fluoxetine, while Byeon et al. (2020) reported the LC50 (24 h) for fluoxetine and sertraline at 1560 µg/L and 507 µg/L, respectively, in the marine rotifer *B. koreanus*. Effect on mortality was also found in long-term exposure: Henry et al. (2004) tested the acute and chronic toxicity of five SSRIs, including sertraline, on daphnid *C. dubia* via water exposure and found that the SSRIs impacted survival: 100 % mortality was observed in daphnids exposed to 0.447 mg/L of sertraline (0.12 mg/L for LC50). Sánchez-Argüello et al. (2009) tested the toxicity of fluoxetine in a two-species (*C. riparius* and a partial life cycle with the freshwater snail *P. acuta*) water-sediment system by continuous application of fluoxetine to the overlying water (31.3, 62.5, 125 and 250 µg/L). They reported a mortality rate of 28 % at low treatment levels (nominal: 31.3; 62.5 and 87.5 µg/L) and less than 7 % mortality in control and higher concentrations (125 and 250 µg/mL) after 24 days of exposure (Sánchez-Argüello et al., 2009). In contrast, Neuparth et al. (2019) exposed the amphipod *Gammarus locusta* chronically to low concentrations of sertraline (8–1000 ng/L) in a water exposure (48 days) and found no significant impact on survival. Similarly, another study also found no significant effect on mortality under SSRI exposure (Schuijt et al., 2023). Flaherty and Dodson (2005) examined the toxicity of individual pharmaceuticals (the SSRI fluoxetine, clofibrac acid, an active metabolite of lipid-lowering drugs) and their mixtures on *D. magna*. They found that exposure to single pharmaceuticals in the 1–100 µg/L range did not result in significant impacts on the normal life processes of *Daphnia*, but a mixture of fluoxetine (36 µg/L) and clofibrac acid (100 µg/L) caused significant mortality: 62.5 % of *Daphnia* exposed to the mixture died by day 6, compared to a 10 % mortality rate among control *Daphnia* (Flaherty and Dodson, 2005).

Possible explanations for the impact on survival could be the disruption of the nervous system and neurotransmitter signalling, such as serotonin reuptake in invertebrates. These impacts will affect vital physiological processes, such as behavioural changes that eventually may lead to mortality. Indeed, Bossus et al. (2014) examined the expression of several neurological genes that are potentially involved in the serotonin metabolic pathway or behaviour regulation in *E. marinus* after exposure to environmentally relevant concentrations (from 0.001 to 1 µg/L) of fluoxetine and sertraline for 8 days. The results indicated that the levels of 3 different genes (*Neuc*, *Rhod1* and *Arr*) were significantly down-regulated by approximately 0.5-, 0.29- and 0.46-fold, respectively, for the lower concentrations of fluoxetine suggesting potential changes in the phototransduction pathway. Significant differences in gene expression were also observed in individuals exposed to sertraline. At the same time, alteration of behaviour (locomotion) was observed as a significant effect (elevation) on velocity (Bossus et al., 2014). This can highly affect the survival of organisms as a disruption in behaviour can affect, for example, feeding, predator avoidance, etc. Undeniably, observing alterations in behaviour can serve as an initial indication of more severe ecotoxicological consequences (Hellou, 2011). Often, the disturbance of one behaviour can cascade into the disruption of subsequent behaviours, with each disruption potentially escalating in

impact level (Fong et al., 2015). We therefore suggest future studies of antidepressants focus on behavioural endpoints in addition to the conventional endpoints (i.e., growth, reproduction, mortality) to increase our understanding of behaviour as a test endpoint.

We found that sediment-associated sertraline affected growth and reproduction negatively. This is in accordance with other studies showing a negative impact of sertraline on the reproduction of invertebrates (both water and sediment exposure) like *C. teleta* and *D. magna* (Henry et al., 2004; Minagh et al., 2009; Lamichhane et al., 2014; Méndez and Barata, 2015; Mínguez et al., 2015; Byeon et al., 2020; Chen et al., 2021). Lamichhane et al. (2014) examined the impact of environmentally relevant sertraline concentrations in water on the life-history characteristics of the water flea *C. dubia* across three generations with water exposure, both in terms of acute and chronic effects: sertraline significantly delayed and reduced reproduction and resulted in fewer and smaller offspring per female across all generations examined. Indeed, various conflicting demands exist on the limited resources accessible to organisms: growth, reproduction, and maintenance/survival. For example, when an organism devotes energy to one function, like maintenance, it may reduce or deplete energy from other processes, like reproduction, according to the principle of energy allocation (Cody, 1966). Sibly et al. (2013) suggested that decreased juvenile number and body size could be related to reduced energy allocation for reproduction. In our study, exposure to high sertraline concentrations presumably required more energy for maintenance and detoxification, reducing available energy for reproduction and growth in adult worms. This represents a trade-off between survival, reproduction and growth. On the other hand, *T. tubifex* exposed to the lowest and most environmentally relevant concentration produced a similar or slightly higher number of cocoons than the control, resulting in a reduction in growth. However, there might also be a trade-off between the quantity and quality of offspring, as there were fewer juveniles than in the control. This could be due to an abnormality in offspring, as mentioned previously, or a reduction of embryos within one cocoon since the number of embryos in a cocoon often vary among individuals (Reynoldson et al., 1991). We suggest pursuing the offspring quality in future studies focusing on multigenerational impact.

In the present study, fewer juveniles were found in the lowest concentrations even though a similar or even higher number of cocoons were produced, suggesting that sertraline affects juvenile survival. Méndez and Barata (2015) assessed fluoxetine effects on juveniles and adult polychaetes (namely *Capitella teleta* and *Capitella sp. A*) by exposing them to fluoxetine-spiked sediment (0.001–3.3 µg/g dw sed.) and reported that fluoxetine reduced feeding in juveniles to a higher degree than in adult *Capitella sp. A*. This suggests an explanation for the reduced number of survived juveniles under sertraline exposure in the present study, as juvenile mortality could be caused by decreased feeding. Besides, fluoxetine may cause morphological abnormalities as observed in, for example, *C. teleta*, Japanese medaka (*O. latipes*), *C. dubia* and *D. magna* (Brooks et al., 2003a; Foran et al., 2004; Méndez and Barata, 2015). Abnormalities in essential structures or organs may impair their ability to perform vital functions, such as feeding, locomotion, or predator avoidance, all factors that may impact survival. Reduced fitness and impaired physiological functioning can make organisms more susceptible to predation, competition, and environmental stressors, ultimately lowering their survival rate (Kramer et al., 2011; Araújo et al., 2020; López-Valcárcel et al., 2021). We speculate that abnormalities may have been induced, thus resulting in the lower survival rate of juveniles exposed to sertraline exposure in our study. Overall, it indicates reproductive repercussions in natural contexts where sertraline is present in the environment.

SSRIs have further been found to strongly affect the copulation process in invertebrates: Méndez and Barata (2015) assessed the effects of fluoxetine on juveniles and adults of *C. teleta* and *C. sp. A* and found that the presence of fluoxetine in the sediment caused significant delays and inhibition of copulation in both species. The exposed polychaetes

exhibited reduced copulatory activity, leading to a decrease in successful fertilisation events. Besides, atypical genital spines can impede copulation as males rely on these strong spines to grasp and secure the female during mating. The disruption of the copulation process might also be explained by the alteration of behaviour or/and disruption of hormones. According to Corcoran et al. (2010), antidepressants are responsible for the alteration of behaviour and endocrine parameters and affecting reproduction in aquatic organisms. Further, SSRIs in the environment may alter benthic invertebrates' appetite, immune system, reproduction, and other behavioural functions (Brooks et al., 2003b; Nation, 2008). Some studies have shown that SSRIs change the physiology of Cladocera reproduction by stimulating the generation of juvenile hormones and ecdysteroids under low-dose exposure while blocking their activities at higher concentrations through the regulation of oogenesis and vitellogenesis (Fong et al., 2003; Campos et al., 2012, 2013).

Additionally, Campos et al. (2013) discovered that SSRI exposure alters the metabolism of serotonin, the development of neurons, and the metabolism of carbohydrates and lipids, altering how energy is allocated to growth and reproduction in *D. magna*. Schultz et al. (2010) also demonstrated that an environmentally relevant concentration of sertraline exposure significantly reduced fathead minnow survival and anatomically altered testicular interstitial cells, but it did not affect fish reproduction under the 21 days of exposure. Further, studies have confirmed that sertraline impacts the reproduction of vertebrates, such as rats, indicated by a significant decrease in sperm number and sperm deformity. This can further impair the sperm's ability to fertilise an egg as these deformities may include abnormalities in sperm shape, motility, and genetic integrity (Hiemke and Härtter, 2000; Erdemir et al., 2013; Madloul et al., 2019). Thus, it might explain why similar effects (i.e., a decrease in reproduction) were observed in invertebrates. Although the specific physiological mechanisms may differ between vertebrates and invertebrates, the impacts on reproductive parameters, such as sperm count and quality, highlight the potential risks of SSRI exposure to the overall reproductive success and population viability of both vertebrates and invertebrates. A possible explanation was the disruption of the hormones, e.g., GPA2/GPB5 (a novel heterodimeric glycoprotein hormone) present in many polychaetes and oligochaetes, which play a critical role in development, metabolism and reproduction as they are involved in the coordination of physiological functions and act as a signalling molecule within the organisms (Paluzzi et al., 2014; Rocco and Paluzzi, 2016; Al-Dailami et al., 2022a, 2022b). Disruption of serotonin levels by SSRIs may impact the GPA2/GPB5 system, altering its release, activity, or receptor sensitivity. Similarly, disruption of another hormone FFamide, which plays a significant role in modulating sexual behaviours, including mating, courtship, and egg-laying in various invertebrates, will also affect reproduction (Veenstra, 2010; Ahn et al., 2017; Zhang et al., 2018; Sharker et al., 2020). By altering serotonin levels and neurotransmitter balance, SSRIs may disrupt the normal functioning of FFamide signalling pathways, leading to changes in sexual behaviours, reproductive success, and overall reproductive fitness in invertebrates. However, other SSRIs with similar serotonin receptor affinity as sertraline, such as fluoxetine, were found to be potent spawning inducers in other invertebrates, like the fingernail clam (*P. moitessierianum*), *D. magna*, *C. dubia* and *H. azteca* (Fong et al., 1998; Brooks et al., 2003b; Flaherty and Dodson, 2005). Both invertebrates and vertebrates respond to SSRIs by increasing serotonin bioavailability. Since serotonin is a neurotransmitter that affects a variety of biological processes in invertebrates, including growth, reproduction, and behaviour, it is believed that its release will lead to an increase in the number of offspring (Nentwig, 2007; Campos et al., 2012; Bossus et al., 2014). Campos et al. (2012) tested if a SSRI-induced increased serotonin postsynaptic activity changes the perception of the food environment by switching life-history responses toward higher food levels by testing a range of endpoints (reproduction, respiration, feeding, survival-starvation assays, lipid, proteins, and carbohydrate levels) in

female *D. magna* exposed to fluoxetine, fluvoxamine and the 5-HT serotonin receptor antagonist, cyproheptadine. They found that SSRIs enhance neuronal activity and carbohydrate metabolism in *D. magna*, and it is possible that SSRIs may elevate aerobic metabolism, resulting in increased energy efficiency in exposed organisms. However, this efficiency may come at the cost of higher oxygen consumption. Overall, SSRI boosts organism capacity for aerobic catabolism, allowing exposed individuals to exploit food resources under normoxic conditions, increasing offspring production without the expense of longevity or growth (Campos et al., 2012). We suggest including an assessment of serotonin levels to increase our understanding of the underlying mechanisms determining behaviour.

In our study, however, it appears that the non-significant but slightly elevated number of cocoons in the lowest concentration (3.3 µg/g dw sed.) came at the price of reduced growth. The difference in the effect of SSRIs on reproduction in invertebrates in various studies may be related to interspecies differences or that multiple mechanisms are acting during the exposure to SSRIs. The limited number of sediment-associated SSRI studies, challenge the ability to compare and understand the differences among studies.

5. Concluding remarks

SSRI impacts on survival, growth, and reproduction can have significant implications for population dynamics in the long term. As discussed above, reduced growth rates can hinder the development and size of individuals, leading to smaller body sizes and potentially limiting their survival and reproductive capabilities. Impaired reproduction, such as decreased fecundity or fertility, likely depress the production of offspring, thus limiting the recruitment of new individuals to the population. Over time, these negative effects on survival, growth, and reproduction can result in a decline in population growth. If the population fails to replace dead individuals or to reproduce at a rate that sustains the population size, it may become vulnerable to local extinctions, or exhibit reduced resilience to environmental stressors (Maes et al., 2008; Echeverría-Sáenz et al., 2022). Furthermore, changes in population size and structure can impact the ecological dynamics of the entire ecosystem – invertebrates play essential roles in ecosystem functioning, including nutrient cycling, decomposition, and serving as a food source for other organisms. A decline in population size can disrupt these ecosystem processes and have broader implications for the functioning and stability of the ecosystem as a whole (Boulton et al., 2008; Hölker et al., 2015). It is suggested that population modelling be performed to better understand the effect of sertraline, and other SSRIs, on invertebrate population growth.

Moving forward, we suggest to focus and prioritize on non-conventional endpoints, like behavioural changes, in assessing the impacts of SSRIs. Behavioural changes can serve as early warning signs and provide insight into sublethal effects that may precede or accompany mortality. Behavioural alteration, such as feeding, locomotion, predator avoidance, and reproduction, can significantly influence an organism's fitness and ecological interactions (Fong et al., 2015). Assessing serotonin levels in tested organisms is crucial when studying the effects of SSRIs on behavioural changes due to the fundamental role of serotonin in regulating behaviour and mood (Ferreira et al., 2023). This knowledge is essential for making informed decisions about using SSRIs and their potential ecological consequences. In conclusion, integrating non-conventional endpoints into toxicity assessments will provide a more comprehensive and accurate evaluation of the ecological risks associated with SSRIs, supporting informed decision-making and the protection of aquatic ecosystems.

CRedit authorship contribution statement

Henriette Selck: Writing – review & editing, Supervision, Methodology, Formal analysis, Conceptualization. **Elettra D'Amico:** Writing –

review & editing, Methodology, Formal analysis, Conceptualization. **Martina Santobuono**: Writing – review & editing, Methodology, Formal analysis, Conceptualization. **Wing Sze Chan**: Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft, Visualization, Validation, Software, Methodology, Investigation, Formal analysis, Data curation, Conceptualization.

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Declaration of Competing Interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

Data availability

Data will be made available on request.

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